

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Tinospora cordifolia- leaves aqueous extract biocidal activity on gram-negative bacteria

Jyoti Jaglan ^{1,*}, Andrew C. Singer ², Praveen Sharma ¹ and Savita Jaglan ³

¹ Department of Environmental Science & Engineering, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana, India.

² NERC Centre for Ecology & Hydrology, Benson Lane, Wallingford, United Kingdom.

³ Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana, India.

GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2022, 19(01), 005–008

Publication history: Received on 19 February 2022; revised on 26 March 2022; accepted on 28 March 2022

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2022.19.1.0120>

Abstract

Tinospora cordifolia- leaves aqueous extract is having strong biocidal properties and used as a main home remedial plant since ancient times. Herbal extraction is having slow-acting properties, so a single dose is not effective as allopathic medicine, perhaps long-term exposure is required. Biocidal activity of leaves aqueous extract is tested using human gastro-intestinal gram-negative pathogenic bacterium *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated from the wastewater treatment plant. Satisfactory results were obtained that confirm the safety of *Tinospora cordifolia* leaves aqueous extraction as an effective home remedial as well as pharmaceutical product due to having effective biocidal properties. To the best of our knowledge, aqueous extraction of *Tinospora cordifolia* leaves with its biocidal activity is first reported in this study.

Keywords: *Tinospora cordifolia*; Aqueous extract; Herbal extraction; Biocide

1. Introduction

Herbal extractions and their bioactive constituents are used as traditional medicine by 80% of the world population reported the World Health Organization [1] among this *Tinospora cordifolia* a member of the Menispermaceae family is a commonly used herb in general Ayurvedic practices. In ancient Ayurvedic practices, this is a commonly used shrub and also known as “Amrutha”, “Gudhuchi” (Sanskrit), “Gurcha” (Hindi). The plant body is a widely spread deciduous shrub with elongated branches. Leaves having long petiole, ex-stipulate, pulvinate, somewhat roundish, simple and alternate, apex and base twisted partially, one way long and halfway round [2]. Plant body bearing juicy stem is creamy or white-grey with thin bark. The flowering season extends over summer and winter bearing yellow florae with stalked racemes. In India, due to diversity rich soil ranging from alkaline to acid, plants grow easily everywhere and need normal humidity levels. Herbal extractions prepared by using the plant *Tinospora cordifolia* are extensively used for different ailments treatment due to having anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, anti-periodic, anti-osteoporotic, anti-allergic antidiabetic and anti-spasmodic, anti-cancerous, cardioprotective properties [3]. Biocidal activity of leaf aqueous extract tested by using human suspected opportunistic pathogenic species associated with Gastrointestinal disease *Aeromonas hydrophila*, a member of genus *Aeromonas*, ubiquitous in the aquatic environment such as River, lake, raw and processed drinking water and domestic sewage [4,5]. Susruta an ancient physician explained various therapeutic and medicinal values of medicinal plants in “Susruta Samhita” [6]. These old traditional practices contain herbal compounds including metals and minerals with well-designed concentrations in a controlled manner for curative and protective effects [7].

* Corresponding author: Jyoti Jaglan

Department of Environmental Science & Engineering, Guru Jambheshwar University of Science & Technology, Hisar, Haryana, India.

Copyright © 2022 Author(s) retain the copyright of this article. This article is published under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License 4.0.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant collection

Tinospora cordifolia leaves were collected from the medicinal and aromatic plants section, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding College of Agriculture, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar Haryana, India. Collected leaves were washed with running tap water then with autoclaved water for proper removal of sand and dust particles.

2.2. Aqueous extraction preparation

Collected leaves of *Tinospora cordifolia* dried in a shady area at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) dried leaves were grounded into powdered form with the help of a grinder. Then leaf powder was stored in a sample container until extraction. Aqueous extraction of leaves was prepared by using Soxhlet (Jain Scientific Glass Works, 18782). Extraction is further subjected to a rotary evaporator/ vacuum oven (Metrex Scientific Instruments Ltd, New Delhi) till obtaining complete extract.

2.3. Biocidal activity

Biocidal activity of *Tinospora cordifolia* leaves extract was performed on *Aeromonas hydrophila* isolated from medical college Sewage Treatment Plant, Hisar (sequence id MN865804.1) with the help of agar well diffusion method [8]. Bacterial culture prepared at 10^6 CFU used for biocidal activity then plated using Mac Conkey media (Himedia). Different concentration like 10 μ l, 50 μ l, 100 μ l of aqueous extract was used for biocidal activity and it was studied at different regular interval of time respectively 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36 hr. All activities are performed in triplicates.

2.4. Data analysis

The biocidal activity graph was plotted by using Origin Pro 8.5 win 10.

3. Results

3.1. Biocidal activity

Figure 1 Biocidal activity of plant extract on *A. Hydrophila*

Agar well diffusion method showed biocide activity of *T. cordifolia* at different concentrations specifically 10, 50, 100 μ L. In 10 μ L Petri plate *A. hydrophila* showed a 23 mm zone of inhibition at 24 hrs while at 30 hr there is no bacterial growth obtained. In 50 μ L Petri plate maximum zone of inhibition observed was 30mm at 24hr incubation. Similarly, there was bacterial growth observed at 30 hrs. In 100 μ L Petri plate at 24 hrs showed a 32 mm zone of inhibition. All three

concentrations provide no bacterial growth at 30 hrs and the colour of the Mueller Hinton media plate turned light brown. Fig 1 shows the biocidal activity of plant extract on *A. Hydrophila*.

4. Discussion

Excessive use of antibiotics in day-to-day life created a life-threatening situation that gives rise to superbug formation [9]. Extensive and without prescribed use of antibiotics helps bacteria in gaining antibiotic resistance through horizontal gene transfer. In such situations, we have to opt for alternative medicine or drug product. Biocide isolated from plants proved a better alternative approach to combat with superbug situation. In our study, we observed that *Aeromonas hydrophila* multiple drug-resistant bacteria that can be effectively treated by using plant extract isolated from *Tinospora cordifolia* [10]. Plant biocides naturally show coevolution that helps to deal with such situations [11]. As the hypothesis clearly explains when pathogen or selective agents become specialized on the genotype of common host sexual reproduction/asexual favouring frequency-dependent selection in the host population increases the production of novel genotype and adaptation rate. Heavy metal impurities or toxicants can be easily removed with the help of biotechnological applications like chromatography, dilution, extraction, ultrafiltration and diafiltration. Further, we can move with biotechnological approaches like conjugates of antibodies and drugs, where elemental impurities can be controlled with small molecular components.

5. Conclusion

Biocides isolated from plants have slow-acting properties but showed effective results on gram-negative antibiotic resistance bacteria. This could be a possible solution to deal with multiple drug-resistant bacteria.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

One of the authors would like to acknowledge UGC SAP II for funding assistance.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] WHO guidelines for assessing quality of herbal medicines with reference to contaminants and residues. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789241594448>.
- [2] Ruthiran P, Ravi L, Selvaraj CI. Phytochemical Screening, FT-IR and Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry Analysis of *Tinospora cordifolia* (Thunb.) Miers. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research*. 2016 Dec 1; 8: 2020–4.
- [3] S S, S G. *Tinospora cordifolia*: One plant, many roles. *Ancient science of life*. Available from: [https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23661861/2012 Apr; 31\(4\)](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23661861/2012 Apr; 31(4)).
- [4] Huys G, Kämpfer P, Albert MJ, Kühn I, Denys R, Swings J. *Aeromonas hydrophila* subsp. *dhakensis* subsp. nov., isolated from children with diarrhoea in Bangladesh, and extended description of *Aeromonas hydrophila* subsp. *hydrophila* (Chester 1901) Stanier 1943 (approved lists 1980). *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol*. 2002 May; 52(3): 705–12.
- [5] Vila J, Ruiz J, Gallardo F, Vargas M, Soler L, Figueras MJ, et al. *Aeromonas* spp. and traveler's diarrhea: clinical features and antimicrobial resistance. *Emerg Infect Dis*. Available from: <https://europepmc.org/articles/PMC2972757>. 2003 May 1; 9(5): 552–5.
- [6] Basalingappa K. *Tinospora cordifolia*: The Antimicrobial Property of the Leaves of Amruthaballi. *Journal of Bacteriology & Mycology: Open Access*. 2017 Nov 8; 5.
- [7] Gurib-Fakim A. Medicinal plants: traditions of yesterday and drugs of tomorrow. *Mol Aspects Med*. 2006 Feb; 27(1): 1–93.

- [8] Farjana A, Zerín N, Kabir MdS. Antimicrobial activity of medicinal plant leaf extracts against pathogenic bacteria. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease*. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2222180814607581>. 2014 Sep 1; 4: 920–3.
- [9] Wu T, Fu L. Chapter 4 - ALK Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitors in Drug Sensitization. In: Chen Z-S, Yang D-H, editors. *Protein Kinase Inhibitors as Sensitizing Agents for Chemotherapy*. Academic Press (Cancer Sensitizing Agents for Chemotherapy; vol. 4). Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128164358000043>. 2019; 4: 45–52.
- [10] Citterio B, Biavasco F. *Aeromonas hydrophila* virulence. *Virulence*. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4601520/2015> Jun 9; 6(5): 417–8.
- [11] Langerhans RB. Coevolution. In: Jørgensen SE, Fath BD, editors. *Encyclopedia of Ecology*. Oxford: Academic Press; Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780080454054004717>. 2008; 644–8.